

An Ultrathin and Lightweight Soft Inflatable Actuator for Natural Tactile Sensory Feedback

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This study introduces a soft inflatable actuator designed to provide rich, multimodal sensory feedback, including both pressure and vibration. The actuator, weighing less than 2 g and with a thickness of 0.4 mm, is a significant improvement over previous designs. Mechanical characterization demonstrates the actuator's capability to produce high-bandwidth vibrations up to 200 Hz and high forces of 28 Newtons at 60 kPa. Psychometric tests conducted with 14 able-bodied individuals and three transradial amputees show performance comparable to state-of-the-art invasive and non-invasive solutions. Furthermore, the actuator successfully conveys different artificial roughness sensations to able-bodied individuals. In a classification task, amputees achieved an overall accuracy of 73.3%, with touch and pressure being the dominant among the elicited sensations. These results highlight the effectiveness, versatility, and lightweight nature of the proposed soft feedback actuator, showing its potential for integration into robotic systems for feedback restoration and augmentation.

human-machine interfaces, multimodal feedback, sensory feedback, soft robotics, wearable haptics

I. INTRODUCTION

The human somatosensory system is fundamental for interacting with the environment, enabling crucial functions like proprioception and the perception of texture, pressure, and temperature [1]. The absence of sensory feedback significantly impairs user performance and engagement in a wide range of applications, including surgical robotics [2], teleoperation[3], and virtual reality [4]. This is particularly detrimental for individuals with sensory impairments such as amputees [5], stroke survivors, and patients with spinal cord injuries. While various haptic feedback systems have been developed to address this need, they often face challenges [6] related to size, comfort, and the ability to provide natural and intuitive sensations. To overcome these limitations, this work presents the design and validation of a lightweight and ultrathin soft pneumatic actuator (SPA) based on thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU). This actuator can produce a rich range of bioinspired, multimodal tactile stimuli, including both pressure and vibration, surpassing the performance of previous soft actuators. The proposed solution

offers a simple, highly customizable, and cost-effective manufacturing process, enabling rapid prototyping and easy adaptation for applications in sensory restoration and augmentation.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The soft actuator is fabricated from two ultrathin 0.2 mm heat-sealable TPU membranes. The desired actuator shapes are first cut using a laser cutter, along with a sheet of heat-resistant paper that defines the internal air chamber. These layers are assembled and heat-sealed at 155°C for 100 seconds. The entire manufacturing process is completed in under 10 minutes, allowing for extensive customization of the actuator's geometry. For this research, actuators with diameters of 10 mm (for fingertips) and 25 mm (for the forearm and residual limb) were produced and evaluated. The actuator's mechanical properties were quantified through a series of characterization tests. An isometric force test measured the force transmitted as a function of inflation pressure, both in direct contact and with induced air gaps. A vibration test analyzed the system's frequency response from 1 to 200 Hz using an IMU to measure peak acceleration. To validate the actuator's performance in a human-in-the-loop context, a user study was conducted with 14 able-bodied participants and three individuals with transradial amputations. The study protocol, approved by the relevant ethics committees, included three distinct experiments: (1) a Just Noticeable Difference (JND) test using a two-alternative forced-choice method to determine pressure discrimination thresholds; (2) a perception-matching test where users compared virtual textures generated by the actuator to real 3D-printed surfaces; and (3) an intensity classification test where amputees categorized stimuli into low, medium, and high

levels.

Figure 1 (A) Detailed structure of the soft actuators, with the two TPU layers (1st and 3rd) and the heat-resistant layer (2nd). (B) Able-bodied mounting for the fingertip and forearm actuators. (C) Mounting of the soft actuators below a prosthetic socket. (D) A direct encoding strategy devised for closed-loop scenarios. Figure adapted from [7]

III. RESULTS

Mechanical characterization confirmed the actuator's robust performance. The 25 mm TPU actuator generated up to 28 N of force at 60 kPa. Crucially, it demonstrated superior performance over a similar nylon-based actuator, especially when an air gap was present; with a 4 mm gap, the TPU design produced approximately 50% more force. The system also exhibited a wide and stable vibration bandwidth, showing a linear correlation between the setpoint frequency and the measured output up to 200 Hz. The peak acceleration consistently remained above the human Vibration Perception Threshold. The user study yielded compelling results regarding the actuator's effectiveness in both delivering force and texture information. The JND analysis resulted in Weber fractions (k) of 20% for the forearm, 19% for the fingertip in able-bodied users, and 22% for the amputee group, indicating a comparable sensitivity between prosthesis users and able-bodied individuals. In the perception-matching task, participants distinguished between the virtual textures—smooth, 1 mm spacing, and 4 mm spacing—with accuracies of 60%, 70%, and 60%, respectively. In the intensity classification task, the three amputees achieved an overall accuracy of 73.3%, substantially exceeding the 33.3% chance level. Analysis of the elicited sensations in amputees revealed that Pressure (25%) and Touch (20%) were the most dominant, suggesting a naturalistic feedback modality. Participants rated the device highly for comfort and pleasantness and indicated a willingness to use it for extended periods. Leveraging these encouraging results, a direct encoding of the sensory information was developed to preserve the richness of the evoked sensations just presented, intended to be used in a closed-loop scenario. The direct encoding implements a piecewise linear function translating the sensor values to actuator pressures. The piecewise function is defined by three regions: an initial constant value, a linear

region and a final constant plateau. The two constant values are fundamental to filter out below threshold readings (the first) and extreme ones (the last plateau).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work extends a previous publication from the same authors [7] presenting an encoding strategy leveraging the promising results of the previous experiments that successfully validated the design and fabrication of an ultrathin, lightweight, soft inflatable actuator for delivering naturalistic and multimodal tactile feedback. The use of TPU offers significant advantages in force transmission, durability, and manufacturing simplicity over existing technologies [6], [8], [9], [10]. The actuator's performance, demonstrated through comprehensive mechanical testing and user studies with both able-bodied individuals and amputees, establishes it as a powerful and versatile tool for human-machine interfaces and sensory restoration for prosthesis users [11]. Its minimal form factor (0.4 mm thickness) and high force-to-pressure ratio make it an ideal candidate for integration into prosthetics, virtual reality systems, and teleoperation interfaces where space and weight are critical constraints. Future research will be directed towards integrating this actuator into a closed-loop controlled prosthetic hand to perform functional tasks such as object size and compliance discrimination.

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